

FRACTURE OF COMPOSITE-METAL ADHESIVE JOINTS UNDER THERMO-MECHANICAL LOADING

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SUMMARY: This paper deals with the problem of the fracture of composite to metal adhesive joints subject to thermo-mechanical loading. The problem is analyzed using a fracture mechanics model, which predicts the critical temperature change at which fracture occurs for a given pair of materials as a function of their thickness ratio. The experimental program carried out to verify the analytical results is described. Thermal tests were conducted on single and double lap joints of metal adhesively bonded to composite. The fracture resistance of the adhesive joint was measured by mechanical testing. It was observed that the steady-state fracture mechanics analysis correctly predicted trends in the critical temperature drop to cause failure as a function of adherend properties. The mechanical tests revealed that scrim-reinforced film adhesives can exhibit resistance curve behavior. It was also noted that a single value of adhesive toughness is not sufficient to characterize fracture data.

KEYWORDS: thermomechanical loading, steady state fracture, adhesive joining, strain energy release rate.

INTRODUCTION

The problem of joining metals to composite materials is increasingly encountered in structural design. Designers in the aerospace industry, for example, have to deal with this issue in various applications ranging from metal facings on composite substructures for increased erosion resistance, through foam-insulated cryogenic tanks, to bonded composite repair of metallic structures. These joints may consist of multiple layers, and ideally are made by adhesive bonding. The reliability of such a joint can often be a major concern, by virtue of the stresses that arise when these dissimilar materials are subjected to thermomechanical loading. Under these conditions, the mismatch in elastic and thermal properties, combined with material interfaces, can result in the fracture of one or more layers, or the interface between them.

In this paper, experimental results are presented for a representative problem of technological interest: single and double lap joints between graphite-epoxy composite and metal adherends subject to purely thermal loading. These data are compared with predictions of a fracture mechanics model [1]. The toughness parameters required to fit the thermal testing data are obtained by mechanical fracture tests. The intention is to provide a conservative lower bound to data, which can be useful for design purposes.

The structure of the paper is as follows: the mechanics of an elastic, brittle, composite-metal lap joint are briefly presented first. Then the thermal testing procedure is described,

along with results and discussion. This is followed by a description of mode I and mode II fracture testing. Finally, the correlation between the theoretical model and the thermal and mechanical test data is discussed.

Fig. 1: Failure modes of a composite-metal single lap joint.

ANALYTICAL MODEL

The mechanics of composite-metal joints can be illustrated by considering single and double lap joints between dissimilar adherends. The problem is simplified by considering the deformations of both layers to be linear elastic and brittle and by ignoring the role of the adhesive. This assumption gives conservative lower bounds for fracture, as in practice, non-linear effects such as plasticity, viscoelasticity or creep of the adherends or adhesive may serve to limit the stress levels in the two materials. Experimental observations of such lap joints under thermal loading show that there are three possible failure modes: debonding of the interface, composite delamination, and matrix cracking [2-4]. These modes are illustrated in figure 1.

The stress and strain distributions on application of a uniform temperature change are obtained using simple beam theory, together with assumptions of equilibrium and the compatibility of curvatures and strains of the two materials [5,6]. They are represented in terms of the following non-dimensional parameters [7-9]

the ratio of layer thicknesses:	$\xi = t_1 / t_2$
the elastic mismatch parameter:	$A = (\bar{E}_1 - \bar{E}_2) / (\bar{E}_1 + \bar{E}_2)$
the ratio of the elastic moduli :	$\lambda = \bar{E}_1 / \bar{E}_2 = (1 + A) / (1 - A)$
and the free thermal strain:	$\varepsilon_t = (\alpha_1 - \alpha_2) \Delta T$

where $t_{1,2}$ are the thicknesses of the layers, $\bar{E}_{1,2}$ are the effective Young's moduli, $\alpha_{1,2}$ are the coefficients of thermal expansion and ΔT the temperature change. In the case of the composite, the material properties in the longitudinal direction are considered.

Interfacial fracture and delamination are modeled as steady-state fracture problems in which the strain energy released as the crack propagates is independent of the crack length. This provides a lower-bound estimate of the thermomechanical loading required for fracture [1,2].

The difference between the strain energies stored in control volumes far ahead and behind the crack tip is equated to the fracture resistance of the bond line. This enables prediction of the critical temperature change for interfacial fracture. For a single lap joint, which is modeled as a bimaterial beam, the strain energy stored (per unit length) ahead of the crack tip is given by the following expression [1,4]:

$$U_{el} = \frac{\beta^2 t_1}{2\bar{E}_1} [3\lambda\xi^3 (\xi + 1)^2 (1 + \lambda\xi^3) + \xi^2 (1 + \lambda\xi)(\lambda\xi^3 + 1)^2] \quad (1)$$

where

$$\beta = \frac{\varepsilon_1 \bar{E}_1}{[\xi(\lambda\xi^3 + 1)(1 + \lambda\xi) + 3\lambda\xi^2 (1 + \xi)^2]}$$

This is the energy released as the joint undergoes interfacial fracture, since the region far behind the crack tip is stress-free. The expression is plotted in figure 2. For a double lap joint undergoing simultaneous debonding of both interfaces, the corresponding expression is:

$$U_d = \frac{\varepsilon_1^2 t_1 \bar{E}_1}{1 + \lambda\xi'} \quad (2)$$

Here, t_2 refers to twice the thickness of the center layer, t_1 the thickness of either of the other layers, and ξ' denotes the ratio of the two. For the case of single interfacial fracture, the strain energy released is the difference of equations (2) and (1), i.e.

$$U_s = U_d - U_{el} \quad (3)$$

This is plotted in figure 3. The strain energy stored in the double lap joint is higher due to the inherent symmetry constraint. This is true for the range of thickness ratios where thin film effects are not prominent.

A similar approach is used to model delamination. The critical temperature drop for matrix cracking, the third failure mode, can be predicted by comparing the maximum transverse stresses in the composite ply groups with its strength in the transverse direction.

Fig. 2: Single lap joint strain energy release rate

Fig. 3: Double lap joint strain energy release rate

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Specimen Fabrication and Materials

To verify the analytical results, thermal loading tests were conducted on metal-composite single and double lap joints. This testing was performed in two stages. In the first stage, 117 mm x 30 mm strips of 6061-T6 aluminum alloy were bonded to strips of 16-ply unidirectional AS4/3501-6 graphite/epoxy composite with the same planform. Single and symmetric double-sided specimens were manufactured with the same composite thickness (2 mm), but varying aluminum thicknesses, such that thickness ratios were between 0.42 and 3.16. These materials and thickness ratios were expected to debond at the interface over a range of temperatures. The specimens were manufactured following a standard procedure [10]. Surface preparation of the metal consisted of light abrasion with garnet paper and subsequent cleaning using a cheesecloth soaked with methyl ethyl ketone. FM 123-2 film adhesive (Cytec) was used for bonding, and the cure was performed at 380°C for 2 hours under 102 kPa chamber air pressure and vacuum.

The second stage consisted of experiments with similar specimens, but included a wider range of material properties and specimen thicknesses. An important difference from the first stage was that the specimens were precracked (to 25 mm from one end). This was done in order to ensure steady state fracture, which was an important assumption in the model. Aluminum or steel (AISI 01) adherends (140 mm x 25 mm) were bonded to AS4/3501-6 graphite/epoxy unidirectional and cross-ply composite laminates. The laminates consisted of 16 or 32 plies, giving a laminate thickness of 2 or 4 mm. The metal thickness was varied between 1.6 and 16.4 mm. The surface preparation of the metal was carried out as before. A mold release agent (MoldWiz™ F-57 NC) was sprayed on each piece of metal over the area to be pre-cracked. The bond cure was carried out as in the previous set of experiments. The thermomechanical properties of the materials used are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Thermomechanical Properties Of Adherends

	Aluminum	Steel	UD CFRP
E_L (GPa)	70	200	141
E_T (GPa)	70	200	10
ν_{LT}	0.3	0.3	0.32
α_L (ppm/K)	24	11	-0.5
α_T (ppm/K)	24	11	30

In parallel, the fracture toughness of the adhesive was measured. Mechanical tests were conducted to obtain the mode I and mode II fracture resistance of the adhesive. The double cantilever beam (DCB) method was employed for mode I, following ASTM standard D3433-93 [11]. Aluminum adherends 152 mm in length, 25.4 mm wide and 12.7 mm thick were bonded together using FM 123-2 adhesive, with a precrack of 25 mm. The surface preparation used was consistent with that used in the thermal testing. The mode II test specimens were similar to those used for end-notch flexure (ENF) testing of polymer matrix composites [12]. These were identical to the mode I specimens, with the exception that the precrack length was 50 mm.

Test Procedure

The thermal test specimens were placed in a liquid nitrogen-cooled thermal cycling chamber which had a low temperature limit of 85 K. The specimens were cooled at a nominal rate of 7 K/min and brought back to room temperature, at which point they were examined for signs of fracture under an optical microscope. The minimum temperature after which fracture was first observed was noted as the critical temperature.

The mechanical tests were performed on a 100 kN capacity servohydraulic testing machine. Data were collected using commercially available data acquisition software. The tests were performed in displacement control at a rate of 0.01 mm/s throughout, which ensured fracture in approximately one minute. Data sampling was at a frequency of 2 Hz. A traveling optical microscope was used to monitor crack extension.

Results

In the first stage of thermal testing, all the specimens failed by interfacial debonding. Figures 4a and 4b show experimental data for the change in temperature to cause fracture as a function of composite-to-aluminum thickness ratio for single and double-sided specimens respectively. Curves of predicted fracture temperature for fixed values of adhesive fracture resistance are also plotted. In the case of the double lap joints, some of the specimens were observed to have undergone fracture at one interface when as they cooled from the cure temperature. This is indicated by arrows in figure 4b. Thus, the double lap joints are more prone to interfacial fracture than single lap joints, as was expected. It is seen that trends in critical temperature drop to cause fracture are correctly predicted, but the scatter in data is considerable. The scatter is attributed to the fact that all the specimens do not undergo steady state fracture; the initial flaw length apparently varied between specimens.

Fig. 4: Thermal fracture data for unprecracked specimens

In the second stage of thermal testing, the mode of fracture was again predominantly interfacial, except in the cross-ply specimens where there was a combination of delamination, matrix cracking and interfacial debonding. The pattern of interfacial debonding was identical in all cases; the fracture always initiated at the metal-adhesive interface and then shifted to the composite-adhesive interface. Figures 5(a-e) show results for each specimen configuration.

It is observed that the scatter in the data was reduced compared to the unprecracked specimens. The predicted fracture temperature drop curves act as lower bounds to the data, but no single value of adhesive toughness seems adequate to characterize the data. The effect of thickness is qualitatively correctly predicted; the critical temperature drop increases with thickness ratio for constant composite thickness, and decreases with increasing composite thickness for the same thickness ratio (see figures 5a and 5d).

(a) $[0]_{16}$ Gr-Ep/Al single lap joint

(b) $[0]_{16}$ Gr-Ep/Al double lap joint

(c) $[0]_{32}$ Gr-Ep/Al single lap joint

(d) $[0]_{16}$ Gr-Ep/Steel single lap joint

(e) $[0_4/90_4]$ Gr-Ep/Al single lap joint

Fig. 5: Thermal fracture data for precracked specimens

The fracture in the mechanical tests was found to be cohesive (i.e. the crack ran predominantly through the adhesive rather than at the interface between the adhesive and metal), and the crack growth was stable. It was observed that both the mode I and mode II toughness values were not unique, but increased with crack length, thus demonstrating resistance curve (R-curve) behavior. There was a marked difference between the initiation values of mode I and mode II fracture toughness (100 J/m² and 900 J/m² respectively). The mechanism responsible for the R-curve behavior was clearly apparent from inspection of the fracture surfaces using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) [13]. As the crack front advanced, the fibers were pulled out of the adhesive at oblique angles, thus dissipating energy and hence increasing the fracture energy required for crack propagation. The role of friction in the ENF tests was uncertain, and it is unclear as to how much this affected the mode II results.

Discussion

In order to compare the thermal test data with the steady state fracture model, values for adhesive fracture toughness were assumed. These were verified by the mechanical test results. The initiation values for the mode I and mode II toughness are approximately 100 J/m² and 900 J/m² respectively. The mixed mode fracture toughness is expected to lie between these two values [9], and this correlates well with the toughness values that can be extrapolated from the thermal test data. It should be noted that the fracture toughness is expected to be a strong function of the mode mixity. This was assumed to be constant at approximately 60° for the metal/[0]₁₆ composite specimens for the range of thickness ratios used, based on results from Suo and Hutchinson [2]. The effect of possible changes in mode mixity needs to be investigated in greater detail.

Additional factors that must be taken into account are the temperature dependence of the adhesive properties and the effect of large scale non-linearity of the adhesive and adherend properties. The cumulative effect of all the above factors needs to be considered to accurately predict the fracture behavior of the metal-composite lap joints.

CONCLUSIONS

The steady-state fracture mechanics analysis correctly predicts trends in the critical temperature drop to cause failure as a function of adherend properties (unidirectional vs. crossply, steel vs. aluminum), adherend thickness, and single vs. double lap joint. However, more detailed modeling is necessary to achieve more precise predictions.

It is apparent that in some circumstances, steady state fracture solutions can provide a useful lower bound to experimental results. This is potentially useful for preliminary design and material selection purposes. Failure mechanism maps can be constructed using these results, which are informative and act as convenient design tools [1].

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